

Features of Translation of Agentive Units in English to Uzbek

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Abstract: *This article analyzes the translation features of English agentive units into Uzbek from a comparative-functional perspective. During the study, the semantic, syntactic and pragmatic features of agent units were studied, and the grammatical and stylistic transformations that occur in the translation process were highlighted. The significance of equivalence, context, and communicative situation in the translation of agentive constructions is also analyzed.*

Keywords: *agent unit, agency, translation, comparative linguistics, syntactic transformation, pragmatic correspondence, equivalence, functional analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

In modern linguistics, the comparative and functional study of language units is considered one of the important scientific directions. In particular, the study of the expression of the category of agency in different languages and its features in the translation process is one of the topical issues of translation studies and comparative linguistics. Agentive units play an important role in the semantic and syntactic structure of the sentence as means of expressing the performer of an action. In English, agency is expressed mainly through morphological and syntactic means, while in Uzbek, this meaning is manifested through grammatical forms, lexical units, and contextual means. In this regard, the process of translating English agent units into Uzbek appears as a complex linguistic phenomenon.

Since English and Uzbek languages structurally belong to different language systems, there are also certain differences in the expression of agentive units. The analytical nature of the English language plays an important role in the formation of agentive constructions, while in the Uzbek language, synthetic methods of expression prevail. As a result, grammatical transformations, syntactic restructuring, and semantic adaptation occur during the translation process. In particular, it is important to preserve the context and stylistic meaning in the translation of agent units formed by suffixes such as -er, -or, -ist in English into Uzbek. This requires a translator to have a deep knowledge of the grammatical and pragmatic features of the two languages.

Although the category of agentiveness is currently widely studied within the framework of functional syntax, pragmalinguistics, and cognitive linguistics, the translation features of English agentive units into Uzbek have not been sufficiently studied. Existing scientific research mainly covers the general theoretical aspects of agency, and less attention is paid to the issue of functional-semantic changes in the translation process. The correct and functionally appropriate expression of agentive units in translation plays an important role in maintaining the semantic integrity and stylistic impact of the text. Therefore, this topic is of scientific and practical importance for modern translation studies and comparative linguistics.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The category of agentiveness is studied in linguistics as one of the important categories representing semantic and syntactic relations. The theoretical foundations of this issue were developed by Ch. It is widely covered in Fillmore's "Case Grammar" theory, in which the agent is interpreted as the primary semantic role performing the action¹. The scientist's views later served as the basis for the development of the theory of semantic roles. In the translation of English agent units into Uzbek, it is also important to determine the grammatical and semantic function of the agent.

M. A. K. Halliday analyzed the communicative and pragmatic functions of agentive units within the framework of system-functional grammar². The scholar emphasizes that agentive constructions play a crucial role in the functional structure of a sentence. This approach is also important for translation studies, indicating the need to preserve not only the formal but also the functional equivalence of agent units in translation. In particular, context and stylistic meaning play an important role in the translation of units formed by agent suffixes in English into Uzbek.

The works of J. Catford and V. N. Komissarov are an important theoretical source in translation studies. Catford³ paid special attention to the issue of grammatical and semantic transformations in translation, while Komissarov provided an in-depth analysis of the problems of equivalence and pragmatic compatibility⁴. In Uzbek linguistics, the works of A. Nurmonov⁵ and Sh. Safarov⁶ on syntax and pragmalinguistics serve as an important methodological basis for studying the functional properties of agent units.

METHODOLOGY

Comparative-analytical, functional-semantic, descriptive, and contextual analysis methods were used in this study. In order to determine the translation features of English agent units into Uzbek, examples from literary, journalistic, and scientific texts were analyzed from a comparative perspective. In the course of the research, the grammatical form, semantic content, and pragmatic function of agent constructions were studied, and the issues of syntactic transformations and equivalence arising during the translation process were clarified. Also, their functional load and communicative significance were analyzed based on the contextual use of language units.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Agentive units are considered one of the important means of expressing the performer of an action within the semantic system of language. In English, agentiveness is mainly formed by morphological means, in particular, through the suffixes *-er*, *-or*, *-ist*, *-ant*: units such as "teacher", "translator", "researcher", "assistant" are examples of this. In the Uzbek language, the agent meaning is expressed through lexical and syntactic means: "o'qituvchi", "tarjimon", "tadqiqotchi", "yordamchi". Ch. Fillmore interprets the agent as a semantic subject that consciously performs an action, emphasizing its central role in shaping the content of the sentence⁷. When translating English agent units into Uzbek, it is important to preserve this semantic center. For example, the translation of the sentence "The researcher conducted the experiment" as "Tadqiqotchi tajribani o'tkazdi" shows that the agent meaning is given on the basis of full equivalence. However, in all cases, direct translation is insufficient, as the

¹ Fillmore Ch. J. The case for case. Universals in linguistic theory. — New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston, 1968. — P. 88

² Halliday M. A. K. An introduction to functional grammar. — London: Arnold, 1994. — 434 p

³ Catford J. C. A linguistic theory of translation. — London: Oxford university press, 1965. — 103 p

⁴ Комиссаров В. Н. Теория перевода (лингвистические аспекты). — М.: Высшая школа, 1990. — 253 с

⁵ Nurmonov A. O'zbek tilining nazariy grammatikasi. — Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 2001. — 232 b

⁶ Safarov Sh. Pragmalingvistika. — Toshkent: O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2008. — 300 b

⁷ Fillmore Ch. J. the case for case. Universals in linguistic theory. — New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston, 1968. — P. 89

grammatical systems of the English and Uzbek languages are of a different nature.

J. Catford explains grammatical transformations in translation by the structural difference between language systems⁸. In English, agent units are often expressed in nominal form, while in Uzbek, they can be expressed through verbal constructions. For example, the sentence “*He is a good speaker*” is translated as “*U yaxshi nutq so‘zlaydi*”. Here, the agent noun “speaker” is replaced by a verbal construction. Such transformations in the translation process stem from the synthetic nature of the Uzbek language. V. G. Gak emphasizes that functional compatibility is important alongside semantic compatibility when translating linguistic units⁹. Because some agent units have different meanings depending on the context. For example, the word “*manager*” can be translated as “*rahbar*”, “*menejer*”, “*boshqaruvchi*”. An incorrect choice by the translator leads to a distortion of the pragmatic meaning.

M. A. K. Halliday analyzes agentive units from the perspective of communicative function¹⁰. According to the scientist, agent constructions in the text represent not only the performer of the action, but also the communicative center. For example, in the sentence “*The government introduced new reforms*”, “*government*” as an agentive unit also expresses the semantics of formality and power. When translated into Uzbek as “*Hukumat yangi islohotlarni joriy etdi*”, this semantic and pragmatic load is preserved. Sh. Safarov notes that within the framework of pragmalinguistics, it is necessary to analyze language units in relation to the communicative situation¹¹. This view shows the importance of contextual factors in the translation of agentive units. Especially in journalistic texts, agentive units enhance ideological and emotional impact. For example, units such as “*fighter*”, “*defender*”, “*supporter*” require stylistic adaptation in translation.

In literary texts, the translation of agent units is more complex. A. V. Fyodorov emphasizes that preserving imagery and expressiveness is one of the fundamental principles of literary translation¹². In English, agent units such as “*dreamer*”, “*wanderer*”, “*survivor*” express not only the subject but also the emotional attitude of the author. For example, the translation of the sentence “*He was a lonely wanderer*” as “*He was a lonely wanderer*” is a stylistically successful option. If this unit is translated as “*traveler*”, the expressiveness of the text decreases. Thus, in the translation of agent units, along with semantic equivalence, stylistic compatibility also plays an important role.

In Uzbek linguistics, A. Nurmonov, while studying the functional characteristics of syntactic units, pays special attention to the role of the subject-predicate relationship within a sentence as a communicative center¹³. It is important to preserve this communicative center in the translation of English agentive units. I. R. Galperin analyzes the expressive and emotional functions of agent units within the framework of text stylistics and shows their role in increasing the effectiveness of the text. Especially in journalistic and artistic texts, the stylistic load of agent units is strong, and preserving this feature in translation is one of the main tasks of the translator. Thus, the translation of English agent units into Uzbek is a complex linguistic process closely linked to grammatical, semantic, pragmatic, and stylistic factors.

CONCLUSION

The analysis showed that English agent units undergo grammatical, semantic, and pragmatic transformations during translation into Uzbek. In English, agentiveness is mainly expressed through morphological means, while in Uzbek, lexical and syntactic methods prevail. Therefore, it is important to preserve not only the lexical meaning of agent units in translation, but also their functional and stylistic

⁸ Catford J. C. A linguistic theory of translation. — London: Oxford university press, 1965. — 103 p

⁹ Гак В. Г. Теория и практика перевода. — М.: Интердиалект, 2000. — 457 с.

¹⁰ Halliday M. A. K. An introduction to functional grammar. — London: Arnold, 1994. — 434 p

¹¹ Safarov Sh. Pragmalingvistika. — Toshkent: O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2008. — 300 b

¹² Федоров А. В. Основы общей теории перевода. — СПб.: Филология Три, 2002. — 416 с.

¹³ Nurmonov A. O‘zbek tilining nazariy grammatikasi. — Toshkent: O‘qituvchi, 2001. — 232 b

features. During the study, it was determined that context, communicative situation, and text style are among the key factors in the translation of agentive units. It was also observed that ensuring equivalence and pragmatic compatibility in the translation of agent constructions is important in maintaining the semantic integrity and effectiveness of the text.

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